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Impact of the ocean mesoscale on the atmospheric mean state

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Executive Summary

We examine the atmospheric mean state in the four EERIE eddy-rich coupled models (IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO, ICON and HadGEM), focusing on the historical period 1979-2015. The biases in key variables such as two-meter temperature, precipitation and zonal winds are, with the exception of ICON, comparable to the biases of past CMIP6 models at lower resolution. IFS-FESOM and HadGEM perform notably well, consistently outperforming the CMIP6 median. IFS-NEMO has a small but consistent cold bias, which is sufficient to make it slightly colder than the coldest CMIP6 model, though the bias at any given gridpoint is small. ICON has particularly large biases in the atmospheric mean state, likely because it does not use convection parameterisations, which results in large biases in the tropics that affect the entire global circulation. However, all models, ICON included, simulate the global top-of-atmosphere energy budget very well, placing them at the forefront of CMIP models in this respect. No clear improvement to the double ITCZ bias is found in the EERIE simulations.

The direct effect of mesoscale eddies on the atmospheric mean state is estimated using the smoothed-SST experiments and compared against the signal in the coupled models. This analysis suggests that the direct effect of mesoscale eddies on the atmospheric mean state is small, though some consistent effects are identified. Firstly, the presence of eddies results in enhanced latent heat fluxes (~ 4 to 10 W/m^2) and precipitation (~ 0.3 to 0.4 mm/day) over eddy-rich regions such as the Gulf Stream and Kuroshio. The enhanced precipitation appears to trigger robust shifts in the North Atlantic and North Pacific jets, though the signals are confined to particular seasons and hard to detect when assessing extratropical cyclone tracks. Secondly, a reduction in total cloud cover of roughly 1-2% is found over the southern ocean. These changes are supported by eddy composite analysis, which show that eddies have a clear local impact on the atmosphere. In all these cases we emphasise that the magnitude of the changes are modest compared to interannual and inter-model variability. In particular, they are much smaller than the spread between the coupled EERIE models, and sometimes opposite to the direction of change between the coupled EERIE models and CMIP models at lower resolution. This implies that the dominant impact of ocean eddies on the atmosphere likely arises indirectly, via the way they change the large-scale SST biases in models by modulating ocean heat and salinity transports, rather than via the direct forcing attributable to transient mesoscale eddies.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and motivation

The EERIE eddy-rich coupled “frontier” simulations are now complete. These comprise the first ever set of HighResMIP-style climate simulations of the period 1950-2015 at ~10km atmospheric horizontal resolution and an ocean resolution high enough to resolve mesoscale eddies, and thus offer a unique opportunity to assess the effect of resolving mesoscale eddies on the climate of the atmosphere. While it might be anticipated that some of the more exciting impacts are on atmospheric variability, for example through the generation of particularly intense heatfluxes across eddy-generated fronts, it is essential to begin by assessing the atmospheric mean state in the eddy-rich simulations. This is because, firstly, in many cases the variability itself is fundamentally dependent on the mean state, and thus the impact of eddies on the atmosphere cannot be clearly understood or attributed without taking into account the model mean state. Secondly, assessing the role of mesoscale eddies on the atmosphere requires a comparison against models run at lower, non-eddying resolutions. Because of the unprecedentedly high atmospheric and oceanic resolution of the EERIE simulations, there is no a priori guarantee that the atmospheric mean state biases of the eddy-rich simulations are comparable to those of lower resolution models (e.g., CMIP6). Indeed, due to the importance of model tuning in setting the mean state, and the difficulty of tuning high resolution models, the atmospheric mean state biases could in theory be substantially larger than those of lower resolution models. Thus a thorough assessment of the atmospheric mean state biases in the EERIE simulations is an important first step when trying to understand the effect of mesoscale ocean eddies on the atmosphere.

1.2. The goals of this report

There are two main goals of this report:

1. To document the EERIE model atmospheric mean state biases and compare them to typical CMIP-model biases. Is there a step change in the simulated climates in EERIE models or are they roughly comparable to CMIP6?
2. Discuss which atmospheric mean state changes seen in EERIE models compared to non-eddying CMIP models may be related to the presence of meso-scale ocean eddies.

For the first goal, we will show and discuss the EERIE biases, and systematically compare these against CMIP6 biases. For the second goal, we rely on two methods. Firstly, we look at how the bias of interest varies with resolution across a wide range of coupled models spanning from CMIP5 to HighResMIP and EERIE, in order to pick out biases that are sensitive to resolution, and also identify where the performance of EERIE models appears to be notably closer to observations or not. Secondly, we make use of the sensitivity experiments carried out in WP9, described in Deliverable Reports 9.3 and 9.4, which explicitly isolate the direct effect of eddies in targeted AMIP-style simulations. The strength of the first method is it allows for a large ensemble size spanning a wide range of resolutions, but its weakness is that many of the relationships one finds there will be due to changes in atmospheric resolution as opposed to better resolved mesoscale eddies. The strength of the second method is that it explicitly detects the impact of eddies, but its weakness is that the ensemble size is small and it only uses two distinct climate models. These two methods thereby complement each other.

We emphasise that the sensitivity experiments are designed to quantify the direct effect of the eddies given the same underlying ocean mean state. Thus they do not quantify the indirect effect the eddies may have on modulating the ocean mean state in the models, and as such will underestimate the total effect of resolving mesoscale eddies. This is discussed further at the end.

For the sake of brevity, the focus of this report is in general on the winter season December-January-February (DJF) and the summer season June-July-August (JJA), though in some cases all seasons are considered.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Model data

We use the EERIE coupled model Frontier Simulations for the historical period 1950-2015, with a focus on the satellite period 1979-2015 for validation against observations. We also make use of the AMIP-style sensitivity experiments. We now briefly describe both sets of experiments. Further details are given in Deliverable D4.1.

2.1.1. EERIE coupled models

The four EERIE models are ICON (MPI-M), IFS-FESOM (AWI), HadGEM-GC5E (MOHC; we refer to this as just “HadGEM” for short) and IFS-NEMO (BSC).

ICON (“ICOsahedral Nonhydrostatic”) is the new framework for the MPI-M Earth system model, described by Hohenegger et al. (2023) and Jungclaus et al. (2022). The ocean component solves the primitive equations (hydrostatic) using conservative schemes on a grid with triangular elements and C-type staggering (Korn, 2017). The sea ice model is based on the finite element sea ice model FESIM (Danilov et al., 2015). A global configuration of ICON-O with a nominal resolution of 10km has been described in (Korn et al., 2022). The atmospheric model uses a nonhydrostatic dynamical core, and is described in Cruger et al. (2018) and Giorgetta et al. (2018). Notably, the configuration of ICON involves turning off all convection parameterisations (the so-called “sapphire” configuration of the model; Hohenegger et al., 2023).

IFS-FESOM uses version 2.5 of FESOM (Finite Element Sea Ice Ocean Model) as its ocean component, configured with an NG5 unstructured triangular grid and 70 depth levels. This configuration provides a minimum horizontal resolution of 5 km in eddy-rich mid- and high-latitude regions and a resolution of approximately 13 km over the tropics (Rackow et al. 2025). The sea ice model is FESIM (Danilov et al. 2015). The atmospheric component is the Integrated Forecast System (IFS) cycle 48r1, developed by the European Center for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), a spectral model run on the triangular-cubic octahedral grid Tco1279 (~10km) with 137 vertical levels. The IFS model configuration closely follows Rackow et al. (2025), except for the treatment of deep convection. While Rackow et al. (2025) used a modified scheme with reduced cloud-base mass flux (see Rackow et al., 2025), we applied the operational IFS treatment.

HadGEM3-CG5 is the latest version of the HadGEM family developed by the UK Met Office Hadley Center (Xavier et al., 2024, *in prep.*) The ocean-ice component is based on the NEMO modelling framework version 4.04. The configuration is GOSI9 (Guiavarc’h et al., 2024). It includes the sea ice model SI3 (Sea Ice modelling Integrated Initiative, Blockley et al., 2024). We focus here on the HH (high atmospheric resolution, high oceanic resolution) version.

The IFS-NEMO model uses version 4.0.7 of the ocean model component NEMO, which includes the sea ice model SI3, both running on a tripolar global orthogonal curvilinear mesh with 75 vertical levels and a horizontal resolution of $1/12^\circ$ (ORCA12), coupled to the same version of the IFS used by IFS-FESOM. It thus differs from IFS-FESOM only in its oceanic component.

Coupled simulations with ICON, IFS-NEMO, and IFS-FESOM were carried out following the HighResMIP protocol (Haarsma et al. 2016). In line with this protocol, a 50-year coupled spin-up was performed using 1950 CMIP6 radiative forcing. From the final state of the spin-up, two

simulations were initiated in parallel: a control run and a historical run. The historical run applied CMIP6 historical forcing from 1950 to 2014 and was integrated for 65 years. The coupled simulations with HadGEM3-GC5 used the CMIP6 protocol (Eyring et al. 2016), with a 200-year spinup with 1850 CMIP6 forcing, followed by a 200-year piControl run and the historical run integrated from 1850-2014. The analysis in this report primarily draws on data from the historical simulation.

2.1.2. Sensitivity experiments

We help isolate the impact of ocean eddies on the large-scale atmospheric circulation using idealised high-resolution global atmosphere simulations conducted with higher and lower resolution configurations of the IFS and HadGEM. The main novelty of these simulations compared to past work is the comparison of results from two state-of-the-art global atmospheric models at unprecedented horizontal resolutions, including multi-decadal IFS simulations with an average horizontal grid spacing of ~9km, which matches the resolution of ECMWF operational medium-range weather forecasts. These coordinated simulations are designed to isolate the response of the large-scale atmospheric circulation (in the absence of ocean feedbacks) to the direct thermodynamic forcing attributable to extratropical SST anomalies associated with transient mesoscale features.

In this deliverable, we explore the impact of extratropical ocean eddies using the following EERIE atmosphere-only experiments:

- **Reference:** EERIE atmosphere-only reference simulations with ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions specified using high-resolution satellite-based estimates of daily-mean sea surface temperatures (SST) and sea-ice concentration.
- **SmoothAnom:** As *Reference*, but daily-mean SST boundary conditions are modified to suppress transient mesoscale SST anomalies in the extratropics. Climatological SSTs are not changed.

Full details of the IFS and HadGEM3 model configurations and experimental design are provided in EERIE deliverables 9.3 and 9.4.

2.1.3. CMIP multimodel data

In order to place EERIE model biases in context, and to explore the effect of increased model resolution, we leverage existing CMIP coupled model data. We use data drawn from a total of 135 historical model simulations, consisting of multiple ensemble members drawn from a range of CMIP6 models (Eyring et al. 2016), CMIP5 models (Taylor et al. 2012), and High-Resolution Model Intercomparison Project (HighResMIP) models (Haarsma et al. 2016). The CMIP5 and CMIP6 historical experiments consist of coupled uninitialized climate runs forced with historical greenhouse gas and aerosol forcings over the twentieth century, after a spinup from a free-running preindustrial control run. The HighResMIP models were initialized in 1950, following a short 50-yr spinup, and they span the 65 years between 1950 and 2015 and use the same historical forcings as CMIP6. The data are in all cases restricted to the December–February seasons between 1979–01 and 2014–12. Thus, CMIP5 data cover 1979–2005 and CMIP6 and HighResMIP cover 1979–2014. The HighResMIP models are sometimes referred to as the “Process-Based Climate Simulation: Advances in High-Resolution Modeling and European Climate Risk Assessment (PRIMAVERA)” models, in reference to the European Union Project under which they were produced. Tables detailing the exact models and ensemble members used are given in Tables 1, 2 and 3 of the Supplementary Material.

In figures of spatial biases, we often show the “CMIP6 median bias”. This involves determining the median across all the CMIP6 models at each individual gridpoint separately. The drawback of this method is that some of the links between different biases will be obfuscated. However, many large scale biases are relatively systematic across models, so this obfuscation is perhaps not too severe.

2.2. Observational data

Our observational product for precipitation is GPM-IMERG (Huffman et al. 2019), a data set which combines satellite measurements to create a gridded product at 0.1 degree resolution spanning 2000 to present. For top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA) radiative quantities, we use CERES-EBAF (Loeb et al. 2018), also spanning 2000 to present. For other quantities we use the reanalysis product ERA5 (Hersbach et al. 2020). For comparison against ERA5 variables the data is always restricted to 1979-2015, while for comparison against GPM-IMERG and CERES the data is restricted to 2000-2015. When assessing tropical and extratropical cyclones, the Japanese Reanalysis for Three Quarters of a Century (JRA-3Q; Kosaka et al. 2024) is also used, along with

the observed tracks obtained from the National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration's International Best-Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS) data set (Knapp et al., 2018).

2.3. Methods

All data is regridded from its native grid to a regular 1 degree grid prior to computation of any metric, except for cyclone tracking, where a 0.25 degree regular grid is used. For sea surface temperatures (SSTs) and sea ice concentration (SIC) the regridding is done using a nearest-neighbour method, and for everything else with a bilinear interpolation.

When assessing the role of horizontal resolution in metrics computed across a range of models we use the nominal atmospheric grid spacing at the equator. For the EERIE simulations this was set to 10km. For the CMIP data the estimated resolutions are shown in Tables 1 to 3; they range from 450km to 25km. By convention the horizontal resolution of any observational dataset is set to 0, to reflect the fact that it is our measure of truth. Note that across all the CMIP models atmospheric and oceanic horizontal resolutions are highly correlated, as modelling centers tend to increase these in tandem from one generation of model to the next. Thus apparent links between atmospheric resolution and a particular atmospheric metric could reflect a causal link from either increased atmospheric horizontal resolution, or increased oceanic resolution, or both. It could also in some cases reflect improved model design or more realistic model forcing data from one generation to the next. We choose to utilise atmospheric resolution as opposed to oceanic resolution because models span a broader range of atmospheric resolutions compared to oceanic resolutions, thus allowing a finer sorting of the models.

3. Assessment of the mean state and biases

In this section we assess the mean state, compare against past CMIP models, and in select cases evaluate the sensitivity to horizontal resolution. The question of what can be attributed to mesoscale eddies is left to the next section.

3.1. Sea surface temperatures and sea ice

We begin by documenting the EERIE model biases in SSTs and SIC over the historical period. We do this for two reasons. Firstly, they will provide essential context for interpreting the atmospheric biases. In particular, any atmospheric mean state changes induced by mesoscale eddies will necessarily be mediated via the SSTs or SIC. Secondly, previous deliverable reports have not yet documented SST and SIC biases over the historical period, due to lack of available data. However, because the impact on the ocean mean state is strictly speaking beyond the scope of this deliverable, the discussion here will be limited and is mostly descriptive. Further analysis on the oceanic mean state was carried out in Deliverable 6.1.

Figure 1: In (a): DJF averaged SSTs in ERA5. In (b): the CMIP6 median DJF SST bias against ERA5. In (c) through (f): DJF SST biases for the four EERIE simulations (IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO, ICON and HadGEM).

Figure 1 shows the SST biases of the EERIE historical simulations during boreal winter DJF (panels c to f), and the CMIP6 median bias (panel b). Figure 2 shows the same but highlighting the North Atlantic region.

Figure 2: As in Figure 1 but zoomed in to highlight the North Atlantic region.

The median CMIP6 bias shows several characteristic features, including an overly warm southern ocean; warm biases in the major cloud deck regions off the western coasts of South America and southern Africa; and North Atlantic biases characteristic of a poorly resolved Gulf Stream (Tsartsali et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2023). The latter Gulf Stream bias can be viewed as a combination of two separate issues: an SST gradient bias near the coast of North America related to the failure of the simulated Gulf Stream to separate from the continent properly, and a “cold blob” bias in the central North Atlantic related to the failure of the model’s Gulf Stream simulating the “northwest corner”, whereby the Gulf Stream turns north due to bottom topography after leaving the continent. The first of these issues (the “separation bias”) is likely strongly related to horizontal model resolution,

while the second issue (the “northwest corner bias”) is very likely related to biases in bathymetry (Chassignet and Marshall 2008).

As reported in Deliverable 6.1 (hereafter D61), while the EERIE models generally show improvements in the simulation of the Gulf Stream, biases remain, especially the bathymetry-related biases of the “northwest corner”. Consistently, we see that IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO and ICON all exhibit a North Atlantic “cold blob” bias of magnitude comparable to a typical CMIP6 model. The notable exception here is HadGEM, which has a substantially reduced cold bias, consistent with its particularly good Gulf Stream simulation (see D61, and also Tsartsali et al. 2022).

Figure 3: In (a): Winter (DJF) averaged Arctic SIC in ERA5. In (b): the CMIP6 median DJF SIC bias against ERA5. In (c) through (f): DJF SIC biases for the four EERIE simulations (IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO, ICON and HadGEM).

Looking globally, we can see that despite the many improvements noted in D61, substantial biases remain. All models except IFS-NEMO still have an overly warm southern ocean, and IFS-NEMO is

likely only excepted from this by virtue of being uniformly too cold temperature, a feature we will see more clearly when we turn to the atmosphere in the next section. We do not comment here in detail on all the features seen in Figure 1, except, firstly, to acknowledge the large biases in the ICON model (e.g. in the tropical Pacific). As will be seen, many of these relate to substantial biases in tropical convection which have a profound impact on the atmospheric and oceanic mean state. Secondly, it is clear that some of the SST biases in the polar regions are related to sea ice (Figure 3 & 4).

Figure 4: In (a): Winter (JJA) Antarctic averaged SIC in ERA5. In (b): the CMIP6 median JJA SIC bias against ERA5. In (c) through (f): JJA SIC biases for the four EERIE simulations (IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO, ICON and HadGEM).

Figure 3 shows Arctic SIC biases in DJF for the EERIE models and the CMIP6 median. Most CMIP6 models have a bias towards too much SIC, especially around Greenland and the Barents sea (see also Notz et al. 2020). This bias is present, and in fact particularly severe, in IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO. ICON and HadGEM have quite different biases, with a clear tendency towards

greatly reduced SIC, except for ICON around Alaska and Siberia. Figure 4 shows that many of these features are mirrored in the southern hemisphere winter ice, though IFS-FESOM shows a more mixed bias, with the sign of the bias correlating with the sign of the SST bias in JJA. An overview of CMIP6 biases here is given in Roach et al. (2020).

For completeness, Figure 5 shows the JJA SST biases. Many of the features are the same as for DJF, with a seasonally induced shift. We do not show the northern and southern hemisphere summer sea ice biases, as the signs of the bias are generally the same as for winter.

Figure 5: In (a): JJA averaged SSTs in ERA5. In (b): the CMIP6 median JJA SST bias against ERA5. In (c) through (f): JJA SST biases for the four EERIE simulations (IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO, ICON and HadGEM).

To get a better sense of how the EERIE model biases in SST and SIC compare to typical CMIP6 biases, we show in Figure 6 histograms of the absolute bias of these variables, pooled across all gridpoints: for CMIP6 we have combined all models to make a single histogram. For SSTs, HadGEM and IFS-FESOM perform relatively well, and ICON performs poorly. Despite having a consistent cold bias, IFS-NEMO's biases at any single gridpoint are entirely comparable to typical CMIP6 biases: its overall cold bias is thus a result of the consistent negative sign of the bias as opposed to the bias at any particular location being particularly negative. For SIC, ICON and HadGEM perform well, but IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO both have biases exceeding the full CMIP6 range.

Figure 6: Histograms of absolute SST and SIC biases. In (a): the absolute bias of various models against ERA5 for DJF SSTs across all gridpoints. In (b): the same but for JJA SSTs. In (c) and (d): the equivalent plots but for SIC. The filled grey histogram is obtained by combining the absolute biases across all the CMIP6 models used. The line contours are always IFS-FESOM (purple), IFS-NEMO (yellow), ICON (blue) and HadGEM (green). Note the log scale on the y-axes.

3.2. Surface temperature and precipitation

We first look at global biases, and then briefly examine the Gulf Stream region and the 'double ITCZ' bias in closer detail.

3.2.1. Global biases

Figures 7 and 8 show the EERIE model biases in DJF two-meter temperature (T2M) and precipitation, along with the corresponding CMIP6 median bias. Biases in T2M mirror biases in SSTs over the oceans. A variety of biases are also present over land, but comparison against the CMIP6 median suggests the magnitudes of these biases are not unusual, with two exceptions. Firstly, the ICON model has substantial biases over, for example, North America, Africa, Australia and the tropical Pacific that are atypical in the CMIP6 ensemble. Secondly, the IFS-NEMO T2M biases are entirely analogous to its SST biases: while the biases at any given location are not particularly unusual, the consistency of the cold bias is noteworthy.

Figure 7: In (a): DJF averaged T2M in ERA5. In (b): the CMIP6 median DJF T2M bias against ERA5. In (c) through (f): DJF T2M biases for the four EERIE simulations (IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO, ICON and HadGEM). Readers are advised that ERA5 is known to be biased warm over the poles: see main text for more.

With regards to the large cold biases seen over the Arctic in several models, it is important to note that ERA5 is known to be biased warm in the polar regions by up to a few degrees (Tian et al. 2024; Bromwich et al. 2024). Thus cold biases over these regions in models are likely to be exaggerated when measured against ERA5. Finally, we note the warm bias over Antarctica in IFS-FESOM. Investigations confirmed that this is caused by a bug in the snow depth initial conditions of the model, which resulted in unrealistically low snow depth values and consequently unrealistically warm surface temperatures.

Figure 8: In (a): DJF averaged precipitation in GPM-IMERG. In (b): the CMIP6 median DJF precipitation bias against GPM-IMERG. In (c) through (f): DJF precipitation biases for the four EERIE simulations (IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO, ICON and HadGEM). Units are mm/day.

For precipitation (Figure 8), the CMIP6 bias is dominated by the perennial ‘split ITCZ’ bias in the tropics, and biases related to the western boundary currents, especially the Gulf Stream and Kuroshio. For these latter biases, the changes to the boundary currents in the EERIE models leads to consistent changes in precipitation by altering the location of warm SSTs, and potentially also due to the resolution of mesoscale eddies. In the tropics, none of the EERIE models notably alleviate the split ITCZ bias in the Pacific and Atlantic. As noted in Section 2, ICON does not use a convection parameterisation, but it is apparent that 10km atmospheric resolution is insufficient to accurately resolve convection, resulting in precipitation biases that are particularly large.

The corresponding plots for JJA are shown in Figures 9 and 10 for completeness. The features are broadly similar to those in DJF but with a seasonal shift. Note that the ICON biases are not as large in JJA as in DJF.

Figure 9: T2M biases in JJA: as in Figure 7 but for JJA.

Figure 10: Precipitation biases in JJA: as in Figure 8 but for JJA.

To further assess the biases in T2M, we show in Figure 11 timeseries of globally and annually averaged T2M for the EERIE models, ERA5 and CMIP6 models. IFS-FESOM is remarkably close to the observed timeseries, while HadGEM is somewhat too warm. Interestingly, despite substantial regional T2M biases, ICON's globally averaged T2M is only marginally biased cold. This suggests that the overall energy budget is likely realistic, and that it is rather the distribution of this energy throughout the system which is biased, something we examine further in the section on energy budgets. IFS-NEMO's noteworthy cold bias is made fully apparent in Figure 11, with the global average falling outside the range of CMIP6 models.

Figure 11: Time series of annually averaged globally averaged T2M (1950-2015). The grey lines are the various CMIP6 models. The other lines are IFS-FESOM (purple), IFS-NEMO (yellow), ICON (blue) and HadGEM (green).

In fact, it falls outside the range of the wider ensemble of CMIP6, HighResMIP and CMIP5. This can be seen in Figure 12a, which shows global mean T2M averaged over the period 1979-2015 for a number of models in this ensemble, sorted according to horizontal atmospheric resolution. Figure 12b shows the analogues plot but for the T2M trend over the period 1950-2015. The trends are visibly in the typical CMIP range, even for the cold-biased IFS-NEMO. This figure also shows that increased resolution has little to no systematic impact on global mean T2M, and a small impact on trends. We expect both these reflect model tuning, on the one hand towards realistic surface temperatures and on the other towards trends that are not too large.

To further assess the precipitation biases we show in Figure 13 zonally averaged precipitation for EERIE models, observations (GPM-IMERG) and CMIP6. The CMIP6 models show a wide spread of biases in DJF. The consistent overestimation of precipitation in the southern tropical belt is the signature of the ‘double ITCZ’ bias (Zhang et al. 2015, Tian and Dong 2020), and the EERIE models evidently have a mixed impact on this bias. In JJA the biases are generally smaller for all models. In general, the EERIE models fall within the spread of typical CMIP6 models. One interesting exception is HadGEM, which produces far too much precipitation in the ITCZ in winter: this bias is clearly visible both in Figure 13a and 7f. The other exception is, as before, the ICON model.

Figure 12: In (a): scatter plot of globally averaged T2M in coupled climate models versus their atmospheric horizontal resolution (km). The black dots are models from the CMIP multimodel ensemble (CMIP5, CMIP6 and HighResMIP). The coloured symbols are IFS-FESOM (purple square), IFS-NEMO (yellow triangle pointing down), ICON (blue diamond), HadGEM (green triangle pointing left) and ERA5 (red star). To the right is a histogram of the global mean T2M values for the CMIP multimodal data, with the coloured lines corresponding to the EERIE models and ERA5. The value of M is the mean across the CMIP multimodal ensemble. The period used is 1979-2015. In (b): the equivalent plot but for the trend in global mean T2M computed over the period 1950-2015.

To get a better sense of how the EERIE model biases in T2M and precipitation compare to typical CMIP6 biases, we show in Figure 14 histograms of the absolute bias of these variables, pooled across each gridpoint: for CMIP6 models we have combined all models into a single histogram. These suggest that IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO perform very well for precipitation in both winter and summer, and IFS-FESOM and HadGEM perform well for T2M in both seasons. Interestingly, IFS-NEMO also performs quite well for T2M, suggesting that while it has an overall cold bias, the bias at any given gridpoint is relatively small, as was the case for its SST biases. HadGEM’s biases

in summer precipitation are also clear here. In fact, the maximum error attained by HadGEM here is more than 100mm/day, achieved at a single coastal gridpoint near Burma (not shown), vastly exceeding the errors of any of the CMIP6 models we considered here. The origin of these rare but large biases is not clear.

Figure 13: Zonally averaged precipitation averaged over the DJF season in (a) and the JJA season in (b). Shown are IMERG (red), IFS-FESOM (purple), IFS-NEMO (orange), ICON (blue) and HadGEM (green). Also shown is the CMIP6 mean (black) and the 2 sigma spread of individual CMIP6 models around this mean.

Another way to assess the magnitude of the EERIE model biases is to compare to biases in AMIP-simulations, where the SSTs are prescribed. Such simulations are not expected to be equivalent to having a bias-free dynamic ocean model, because the lack of coupling in AMIP-simulations impacts the simulated variability (Barsugli and Battisti 1998). However, they give useful insight into the approximate magnitude of bias you might still have even with such a bias-free dynamic ocean.

Figure 14: Histograms of absolute precipitation and T2M biases. In (a): the absolute bias of various models against IMERG for DJF precipitation across all gridpoints. In (b): the same but for JJA precipitation. In (c) and (d): the equivalent plots but for T2M biases against ERA5. The filled grey histogram is that obtained by combining the absolute biases across all the CMIP6 models used. The line contours are always IFS-FESOM (purple), IFS-NEMO (yellow), ICON (blue) and HadGEM (green). Note the log scale in (a) and (b).

Figure 15 shows the DJF precipitation biases in four such AMIP simulations (the high and low-resolution IFS and HadGEM models). Comparison with Figure 7 suggests that the biases are actually comparable in magnitude in many areas. In particular, comparing the HadGEM AMIP simulations with the HadGEM coupled simulation, considerable overlap between the biases is apparent, suggesting a purely atmospheric origin for much of the precipitation bias. On the other hand, comparing the IFS AMIP simulations with the coupled IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO simulations in Figure 7 suggests the coupled biases are somewhat different and often larger in magnitude. Thus while a large amount of the precipitation bias is due to the atmospheric model, inadequacies in the ocean or atmosphere-ocean coupling can easily change the bias, including making it worse.

Figure 15: DJF biases in precipitation against IMERG for the four AMIP Reference simulations: IFS-AMIP-LR in (a), IFS-AMIP-HR in (b), HadGEM-AMIP-LR in (c) and HadGEM-AMIP-HR in (d).

3.2.2. Gulf Stream Precipitation

Precipitation in the Gulf Stream region in DJF has been linked to high-impact atmospheric events, such as European Blocking, and precipitation in this region has also been shown to be modulated by the SST fronts generated by eddies. We therefore briefly examine precipitation in this region more closely. Figure 16 shows the DJF precipitation biases in the North Atlantic sector, with the black box highlighting a Gulf Stream region, which we define as 35-45N, 70-50W following past conventions. Figure 17(a) shows the mean precipitation in this region across a range of CMIP models at various atmospheric resolutions, while (b) shows the 99th percentile of daily precipitation, computed across all grid points in the domain, again as a function of atmospheric resolution.

Figure 16: DJF precipitation biases: as in Figure 8 but zoomed in to the North Atlantic sector.

This shows that both the mean precipitation, and the magnitude of extremes, go up relatively linearly as resolution increases, especially the latter; this result was first published in Strommen et al. (2025). The mean bias is small on average across CMIP models, including the EERIE simulations. As expected, models struggle more to simulate extreme precipitation, with a persistent underestimation for most CMIP models. The EERIE models are clearly among the best performing models overall here, especially for extremes. Indeed, the magnitude of EERIE model precipitation extremes are more or less exactly what one would estimate for a 10km atmospheric resolution, based on extrapolation of past model behaviour.

An interesting point here is that the predecessor to IMERG, the TRMM3B42 data set, estimated a precipitation maxima in this region 50% greater than IMERG, leading to considerable uncertainty in what the true value is in the real world. The fact that the EERIE models are consistent with IMERG suggest that IMERG may indeed provide a more realistic estimate than TRMM (see Strommen et al. 2025 for further discussion on this).

Figure 17: In (a): scatter plot of Gulf Stream averaged precipitation in coupled climate models versus their atmospheric horizontal resolution (km). The black dots are models from the CMIP multimodel ensemble (CMIP5, CMIP6 and HighResMIP). The coloured symbols are IFS-FESOM (purple square), IFS-NEMO (yellow triangle pointing down), ICON (blue diamond), HadGEM (green triangle pointing left) and IMERG (red star). To the right is a histogram of the global mean T2M values for the CMIP multimodal data, with the coloured lines corresponding to the EERIE models and ERA5. The value of M is the mean across the CMIP multimodal ensemble. The period used is 2000-2015. In (b): the equivalent plot but for the 99th percentile of Gulf Stream precipitation (computed across all gridpoints in the domain).

3.2.3. The double ITCZ bias

A pervasive and persistent model bias in precipitation is the so-called double or split ITCZ bias. In the tropical Pacific, the precipitation of the intertropical convergence zone (ITCZ) splits into two local maxima, but models tend to heavily overestimate the extent of this split. In JJA, this bias is highlighted by the black box in Figure 10b. Past studies have given somewhat conflicting views on

whether horizontal atmospheric resolution can reduce this bias, with no improvement in for many models (Zhou et al. 2022) but an apparent improvement for some select models (e.g. Dong et al. 2025). Figure 18 shows the mean JJA precipitation in the black box of Figure 10b (15S-3S, 180W-230W) for past CMIP models, the EERIE simulations and IMERG observations. It can be seen that there is no clear improvement with resolution, and even at the very high resolutions of the EERIE simulations, there is no systematic improvement in the split ITCZ bias. Our conclusion therefore is the same as in Zhou et al. (2022), that neither the ability to resolve mesoscale eddies nor the 10km atmospheric resolution are sufficient to eliminate the double ITCZ.

Figure 18: Scatter plot of the Pacific double ITCZ (see text) in JJA in coupled climate models versus their atmospheric horizontal resolution (km). The black dots are models from the CMIP multimodel ensemble (CMIP5, CMIP6 and HighResMIP). The coloured symbols are IFS-FESOM (purple square), IFS-NEMO (yellow triangle pointing down), ICON (blue diamond), HadGEM (green triangle pointing left) and IMERG (red star). To the right is a histogram of the global mean T2M values for the CMIP multimodal data, with the coloured lines corresponding to the EERIE models and IMERG. The value M in the histogram title is the mean over models. The period used is 2000-2015.

3.3. Vertical profiles of temperature and zonal winds

While the most immediate imprint of eddies will be on surface variables, such surface changes could in turn lead to circulation shifts aloft. We thus show here changes to zonally averaged air temperature and zonal winds at multiple pressure levels. We focus on JJA because this is when we see the most robust impacts of eddies in the sensitivity experiments later (upcoming Section 4).

Figure 19: Zonally averaged JJA air temperature at various pressure levels. In (a): ERA5, (b): the CMIP6 median bias against ERA5, (c) the IFS-FESOM bias, (d) the IFS-NEMO bias, (e) the ICON bias and (f) the HadGEM bias. In (b)-(f) the black contours show the observations from (a).

Figure 19 shows the vertical profile of air temperature biases in JJA, along with the CMIP6 median bias. CMIP models have shown a tendency towards a cold bias in the troposphere for many years, related to biases in the climatological distribution of relative humidity (John and Soden 2007). The EERIE simulations show mixed performance in this regard. IFS-FESOM and HadGEM both perform notably well in this regard, with the exception of the atmosphere over Antarctica in HadGEM, where its biases are typical of lower resolution CMIP models. We note that the corresponding plot for DJF shows that the Antarctic warm bias of IFS-FESOM seen in Figure 7 extends up to around 500hPa (not shown), so that both HadGEM and IFS-FESOM struggle over Antarctica in particular seasons. IFS-NEMO is biased cold, but not unusually so at any particular location. ICON shows clear evidence of large biases in its overturning circulation.

Figure 20: Zonally averaged JJA zonal winds at various pressure levels. In (a): ERA5, (b): the CMIP6 median bias against ERA5, (c) the IFS-FESOM bias, (d) the IFS-NEMO bias, (e) the ICON bias and (f) the HadGEM bias. In (b)-(f) the black contours show the observations from (a).

Figure 20 shows the equivalent plot for zonal winds. The CMIP6 median bias is somewhat less easy to interpret here, because many individual model biases correspond to different latitudinal displacements of the jet, and these are not clearly visible in the median. However, we note two features: a tendency for an overly strong tropical circulation, and for a northern hemisphere jet that ~~that~~ is too strong near the surface. IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO and HadGEM all confirm more or less to this picture, with their biases being typical of CMIP6 models. ICON's substantial biases in its overturning circulation are, on the other hand, even more evident here.

3.4. Energy and water budgets

The top-of-atmosphere (TOA) energy budget quantifies the net amount of energy entering and leaving the climate system, with the difference between the two, the energy imbalance, being a measure of the magnitude of climate change taking place (Hartmann et al. 1986, Wild 2020). As such, it forms an important part of climate model assessment. The water budget measures the discrepancy between the long-time global mean total precipitation and evaporation, which should be zero due to mass conservation (Trenberth et al. 2007). Its assessment for models thus constitutes a test of a model's ability to conserve mass. Figure 21 shows the TOA imbalance over the period 2000-2005 and TOA trend estimates over 1950-2015. Note that IFS-NEMO could not be added to this figure due to insufficient data to close the budget. CERES estimates the real imbalance as around 0.7 W/m^2 . Most models have imbalances in this range, including the EERIE models. Note that a number of models have negative TOA imbalances, despite the fact that all models have positive T2M trends (Figure 12b). This is due to lack of energy conservation, whereby the net surface imbalance can differ considerably from the TOA imbalance. Figure 21(b) shows that the TOA trend in recent years is substantially underestimated by CMIP models, including the EERIE simulations. Such an underestimation has been reported previously (Olonsheck and Rugenstein 2024), and is likely related to a recent drop in observed aerosol emissions that is missing in models (Hodnebrog et al. 2024). As such, this discrepancy is likely unrelated to resolution or the presence of ocean eddies.

Figure 22 shows the net short and longwave components making up the TOA imbalance. This reveals a more encouraging picture, with a clear progression from low to high-resolution models, with the highest resolution EERIE models being among the closest fits to observations. This is plausibly more related to model development rather than model resolution, with later generations of models having (a) better aerosol schemes and (b) more realistic water absorption in the atmosphere due to better radiation schemes (Wild 2020). The good performance of EERIE models here is therefore consistent with them being at the forefront of coupled climate model development. It is interesting to note that this is also true for ICON, consistent with the hypothesis that its large biases are primarily a result of how the energy is distributed through the system as opposed to biases in the energy budget per se.

Figure 21: In (a): scatter plot of globally averaged net TOA energy imbalance in coupled climate models versus their atmospheric horizontal resolution (km). The black dots are models from the CMIP multimodel ensemble (CMIP5, CMIP6 and HighResMIP). The coloured symbols are IFS-FESOM (purple square), IFS-NEMO (yellow triangle pointing down), ICON (blue diamond), HadGEM (green triangle pointing left) and CERES-EBAF (red star). To the right is a histogram of the TOA imbalance values for the CMIP multimodal data, with the coloured lines corresponding to the EERIE models and CERES-EBAF. The value of M is the mean across the CMIP multimodal ensemble. The period used is 2000-2015. In (b): the equivalent plot but for the trend in global mean T2M over the period 1950-2015.

Turning to the water budget, Figure 23 shows both globally averaged precipitation and global precipitation minus evaporation (P minus E) over the historical period 1979-2015. There has been an overall tendency for precipitation to increase with resolution, plausibly due to higher resolution models simulating larger precipitation extremes.

Figure 22: In (a): scatter plot of globally averaged TOA shortwave radiation in coupled climate models versus their atmospheric horizontal resolution (km). The black dots are models from the CMIP multimodel ensemble (CMIP5, CMIP6 and HighResMIP). The coloured symbols are IFS-FESOM (purple square), IFS-NEMO (yellow triangle pointing down), ICON (blue diamond), HadGEM (green triangle pointing left) and CERES-EBAF (red star). To the right is a histogram of the net shortwave values for the CMIP multimodal data, with the coloured lines corresponding to the EERIE models and CERES-EBAF. The value of M is the mean across the CMIP multimodal ensemble. The period used is 2000-2015. In (b): the equivalent plot but for the new longwave radiation.

However, the large spread suggests that the details of a model’s convection parameterisation plays a big role in the total amount of precipitation simulated; orography also likely plays a role. In general all models overestimate global precipitation relative to IMERG, especially over the tropics (Figures 7 and 10), though it must be kept in mind that there are large uncertainties in the IMERG observational estimate.

Figure 23: As in figure 22 but for (a) globally averaged precipitation and (b) globally averaged precipitation minus evaporation. In (a) we have marked both IMERG (red star) as our best estimate as well as ERA5 (grey star) for additional context. In (b) we have shown ERA5 (red star) for context (the value in the real world is 0).

Interestingly, the higher resolution models are broadly aligned with the estimate from ERA5, suggesting that perhaps the more recently developed, higher resolution models are becoming more realistic at capturing the large scale water budget (which reanalysis products capture by virtue of their construction), but that big biases remain in the drizzle problem (Chen et al. 2021) resulting in excessive precipitation. This would be consistent with the results of Zhou et al. (2022). HadGEM and ICON are notable here in that they substantially overestimate total precipitation, occupying the outer range of past CMIP models. In terms of water conservation, all EERIE models conserve water near-perfectly. However, this is due to the implementation of mass-fixers in these models, which artificially forces perfect conservation. It can be seen that a large number of CMIP

models also have such near-zero P-E, consistent with the widespread use of such mass-fixers, or the construction of models with energy and mass conservation as key targets. Models that do not use such fixers, or have not been built from the onset to be conservative, display a wide range of large positive and negative values, indicative of the general difficulty of conserving mass and energy. Indeed, constraining the models with observations would still not guarantee conservation, as demonstrated by the P-E bias of ERA5 shown in the figure.

3.5. The stratospheric polar vortex

Polar vortices are a prominent feature of the winter stratospheric climatology at high latitudes, with two counterparts in the Northern Hemisphere (NH) and Southern Hemisphere (SH). Their representation in climate models is known to be sensitive to both vertical and horizontal resolution, and many state-of-the-art models struggle to reproduce an adequate strength and/or lifecycle of the vortices, especially in the Southern Hemisphere (e.g. Rao et al. 2022, Feng et al 2024). It is therefore constructive to evaluate how the EERIE models capture the climatological seasonal cycle of these two vortices.

To describe the mean state of the NH and SH vortex we examine the monthly climatology of the zonal-mean zonal wind at 10 hPa at 60°N and 60°S, respectively. We compare the results for the EERIE models with ERA5 and with 6 HighResMIP models (CMCC-CM2-VHR4, CNRM-CM6-1-HR, HadGEM3-GC31-HM, MPI-ESM1-2-XR, EC-Earth3P-HR, ECMWF-IFS-HR) with horizontal resolution between 25 and 100 km.

Figure 24(a) displays the results for the NH. The EERIE models show an overall good performance and capture well the amplitude of the winter peak, in line with results from HighResMIP. A notable exception is again ICON, which simulates a too strong vortex, likely a result of the broader atmospheric biases arising from the lack of convection parameterisations. The EERIE models also simulate properly the timing of the vortex formation (August-September), peak (December-January) and breakdown (around April), except for IFS-NEMO that tends to anticipate them by 1-2 months.

The corresponding results for the SH are presented in Fig. 24(b). Here, the vortex is expected to start forming around March, peak in August and break down in November, with an overall much stronger amplitude than its NH counterpart. The EERIE models deliver mixed performances.

IFS-FESOM is remarkably close to ERA5, while IFS-NEMO reproduces the correct amplitude but again tends to shift the full cycle by about 1 month. HadGEM exhibits a too strong and persistent vortex, although still within the range of the HighResMIP models. In contrast, ICON performs again poorly compared to both the EERIE and HighResMIP models: not only is the vortex consistently too strong, but it also seems to never fully dissolve as no real reversal of the zonal wind occurs.

Figure 24: Climatological seasonal cycle of the stratospheric polar vortex in the Northern Hemisphere (left) and Southern Hemisphere (right). Note the different scale on the vertical axis.

3.6. Tropical and extratropical cyclones

Extreme weather events such as tropical and extratropical cyclones (TCs and ETCs) have direct socio-economic impacts including floods, wind damage, and storm surges. These systems transport heat, momentum, and moisture across large distances and produce much of the seasonal precipitation in both tropics and midlatitudes. Storm characteristics such as size, maximum intensity, and frequency therefore need to be realistically simulated in GCMs to ensure their accuracy and reliability in future climate projections.

The key physical processes affecting storm development often occur at scales smaller than those resolved by the GCMs, which has previously restricted their use for global storm climatology assessments (Lockwood et al. 2025, Bourdin et al. 2024, Baker et al. 2024, Roberts et al. 2020, Priestley et al. 2022, Jiayang et al. 2020). Recent studies have highlighted the need for global storm-resolving models, with resolutions in the range 28–2.8 km in the atmosphere and 28–5 km in the ocean to improve the representation of tropical and extratropical cyclones. The impact of

horizontal resolution on tropical and extratropical cyclones have been investigated through the CMIP6 High Resolution Model Intercomparison Project (HighResMIP; Haarsma et al. 2016). Significant improvements in simulated tropical and extratropical cyclone mean state such as frequency, intensity, spatial distribution and wind structure with increasing resolutions from 100 km to 25 km have been reported (Baker et al. 2024, Roberts et al. 2020, Priestley et al. 2022, Jiayang et al. 2020). The EERIE models employ a much higher resolution (~10 km) and can explicitly resolve mesoscale ocean eddies and convective processes. In addition to assessing the improvements across models and resolutions, the sensitivity experiments offer the opportunity to isolate the impacts of ocean mesoscale eddies on the mean storm climatology.

The EERIE models used in the evaluation of storm climatology are summarized in Table 3.7.1. Tropical and extratropical cyclones are diagnosed from the re-gridded model outputs using a feature-tracking algorithm TempestExtremes (Ullrich and Zarzycki 2017; Zarzycki and Ullrich 2017). Candidate TCs (or nodes) are identified every 6 hours by using a closed-contour criterion, i.e. a sea-level pressure increase of ≥ 2 hPa over 5.5° from pressure minima. The presence of an upper-level warm core characteristic of TC is identified by a geopotential thickness, $Z_{250}-Z_{500}$, decrease of ≥ 6 m ($58.8 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$) over 6.5° from a reference $Z_{250}-Z_{500}$ maximum within 1° of a given pressure minimum. The candidate TCs within 6° are stitched in time into cyclone tracks with a minimum duration of 60 hours and a minimum track length of 8° , which eliminates stationary features and spurious shallow lows. Candidate ETCs are also identified similarly, except the closed-contour criterion is that the sea-level pressure increases by ≥ 2 hPa over 6° from pressure minima, and the candidates with a warm-core are rejected. The candidate ETCs within 6° are stitched in time into cyclone tracks with a minimum duration of 60 hours and a minimum track length of 12° .

We also diagnose TC/ETC tracks from two reanalysis datasets: ERA5 and the JRA-3Q. In addition, the tracks derived from the model outputs from the HighResMIP/PRIMAVERA project are also presented for comparison. We have only included TC tracks from the coupled (hist-1950) HighResMIP/PRIMAVERA models that were run at a higher resolution of 25-50 km in the comparison (Roberts et al. 2020), which are also summarized in Table 3.7.1. Note that the corresponding ETC tracks are not currently available from HighResMIP/PRIMAVERA.

Institution	Model	Model type	Horizontal resolution		Period
MOHC	HadGEM3-GC5	Atmosphere-only (UM)	MR (N216) atm: ~60 km	HR (N640) atm: ~20 km	1980-2023
ECMWF	ECMWF-IFS	Atmosphere-only (IFS)	LR (tco399) atm: ~28 km	HR (tco1279) atm: ~9 km	1980-2023
MOHC	HadGEM3-ORCA	Coupled (NEMO v4.0.4)	MM (N216) ocean: 0.25° atm: ~60 km	HM (N640) ocean: 1/12° atm: ~20 km	1850-2014
AWI	IFS-FESOM	Coupled (FESOM 2.5)		HR (tco1279) ocean: 13-4.5 km atm: ~9 km	1950-2014
MPI-M	ICON	Coupled (ICON-O v2.6.6)		HR (R2B8) ocean: ~5km atm: ~10 km	1950-2014
MOHC/ UoR/ NERC	HadGEM3-GC3.1	Coupled		HM (N512) atm: ~25 km	1950-2014
KNMI / SMHI / BSC	EC-Earth3P	Coupled		HR (T1511) atm: ~36 km	1950-2014
CERFACS	CNRM-CM6.1	Coupled		HR (T1359) atm: ~50 km	1950-2014
MPI	MPI-ESM1.2	Coupled		XR (T255) atm: ~34 km	1950-2014
ECMWF	ECMWF-IFS	Coupled		HR (tco399) atm: ~25 km	1950-2014

Table 3.7.1. Description of EERIE and HighResMIP/PRIMAVERA models used for TC/ETC tracking. The blue text highlights the HighResMIP data.

The model simulated TCs are compared with the IBTrACS data set. Following Roberts et al. (2020), a tropical storm (excluding all subtropical storms or SS) with 1-min maximum sustained winds of 34 kt (17.5 ms^{-1}) or higher is identified as an observed tropical cyclone. The ETC tracks derived from ERA-5 reanalysis is used to compare the model simulated ETCs, due to the lack of available observed ETC tracks.

3.7.1 Tropical cyclones

Key findings:

- ICON significantly overestimates the number of tropical cyclones, in both hemispheres.
- HadGEM3-ORCA and IFS-FESOM simulates too many TCs in the Western Northern Pacific (WNP), South Pacific (SP), and South Indian (SI) basins, and too few in Eastern Northern Pacific (ENP) and North Atlantic basins (NATL).
- Overall, the biases in the coupled simulations are larger compared to the multi-model mean from coupled HIGHRESMIP/PRIMAVERA simulations. However, the small biases seen in the multi-model mean is only due to the inclusion of MPI-ESM and EC-Earth3P which significantly underestimates the track densities.
- All models overestimate the storm durations and underestimate the storm densities and intensification rates, with improvements seen with increase in resolution.
- HADGEM3-ORCA performs well in simulating stronger and more short-lived storms, given its coarse resolution (~20 km) compared to other coupled models. ICON simulates similar intensification rates as Obs, but this is likely to be due to extremely favourable but non-physical environments.

Figure 25 shows the global annual TC activity detected in models, reanalysis, and observations. The total TC frequency increases with resolution for both the atm-only (HadGEM3-GC5) and coupled (HadGEM3-ORCA), as well as for ECMWF-IFS. The high-resolution members of HadGEM3 model tend to overestimate the total number of TCs compared to observations, while the proportion of TCs in the West North Pacific (WNP) decreases. The ICON-ESM model also significantly overestimates the total TC activity but underestimates the WNP activity. Overall, the medium-resolution members of HadGEM3 (60 km) and the high-resolution members of ECMWF-IFS (i.e. ECMWF-IFS and IFS-FESOM2) are more comparable with the observations and reanalysis.

The mean bias in annual TC track density, which is defined as the mean number of tracks in a 4° cap, is shown in Figure 26. For TCs, the bias is computed with respect to IBTRACs (Obs). The HadGEM3-GC5 exhibit positive biases in the WNP basin, and negative biases in the ENP and NATL basins, all of which are enhanced in the coupled model (HadGEM3-ORCA). Although the increased resolution in HadGEM3-GC5 decreases the bias in the NATL and ENP basin, the positive biases in the other basins including the SP and SI are enhanced. The improvements are

less in the coupled model (HadGEM3-ORCA). Increasing resolution in atm-only ECMWF-IFS model also results in small improvements across all basins, but the biases are enhanced in the coupled IFS-FESOM2 model. The coupled ICON-ESM exhibits large positive biases across most of the basins, with the exception of WNP, where the biases are negative. Overall, the biases in atm-only models (except HadGEM3-GC5-HR) are comparable to the reanalysis as well as to the multi-model mutli-ensemble average of the HighResMIP/PRIMAVERA models.

Figure 25: Annual tropical cyclone frequency in different basins from models, reanalysis and observations during historical period (1983-2013). The mean annual TC numbers are indicated in the center. The TC tracks in models and reanalysis are diagnosed using TempestExtremes. The top row indicates the atm-only EERIE simulations (highresSST-present) and bottom row indicates the coupled EERIE simulations (hist-1850 and hist-1950). The thickness of the doughnut is scaled to the total TC observed frequency [i.e., doughnuts thicker than in (k) indicate more TCs, and thinner than in (k) indicate fewer TCs].

The distribution of different TC characteristics such as TC lifetime or duration, intensity, latitude of maximum intensity, and intensification rate diagnosed in the EERIE models, reanalysis and observations are shown in Figure 27. Most of the EERIE models overestimate the TC duration compared to Obs but have similar TC durations compared to reanalysis. The notable exceptions

are the HadGEM3 models, which tend to produce more short-lived TCs. As expected, the high-resolution models tend to produce more intense TCs, with values of maximum 10-m winds (v_{max}) or minimum sea-level pressure (p_{min}) more comparable to Obs and JRA3Q. On the other hand, the low-resolution members in HadGEM3 produce similar intensity distributions as ERA5 reanalysis. Most models fail to simulate TCs stronger than Cat-4 ($v_{max} > 58 \text{ ms}^{-1}$). Similarly to intensity, the high-resolution models also simulate greater intensification rates compared to low-resolution members; however, they still fail to simulate strongly intensifying storms, particularly those undergoing rapid intensification (with intensification rates $> 15 \text{ ms}^{-1}/24 \text{ hr}$).

The accumulated cyclone energy (ACE) index (Bell et al. 2000) is defined as the sum of the square of the maximum sustained 10m wind speed every 6 h while the cyclone is at least tropical storm strength (34 kt; 17.5 ms^{-1}). However, since the model simulated TCs have lower wind speeds, the ACE is calculated for the entirety of the storm. The mean values of ACE are underestimated in all of the models compared to both Obs and reanalysis, which can be attributed to the weaker TC intensities simulated in the models. The model TCs also tend to be located more poleward compared to observations at the time of maximum intensity, which is consistent with previous studies.

Figure 26: Annual tropical cyclone density (storms transits per 4° cap) from IBTRACs (Obs), and track density bias in models during historical period (1983-2013). The top row indicates the atm-only EERIE simulations (highresSST-present) and middle row indicates the coupled EERIE simulations (hist-1850 and hist-1950). The two reanalysis products used for comparisons are ERA5 and JRA3Q, and the HighResMIP ensemble average includes the high-resolution members of the coupled models (hist-1950): CNRM-CM6-1, EC-Earth3P, ECMWF-IFS, HadGEM3-GC31, and MPI-ESM1-2.

Figure 27 Probability distributions of TC characteristics: (a) Duration, (b) maximum 10-m winds (v_{max}), (c) minimum sea-level pressure (p_{min}), (d) accumulated cyclone energy (ACE), (e) latitude of maximum lifetime intensity, and (f) intensification rate.

3.7.2 Extratropical cyclones

Key findings:

- In ICON, ETC track densities are significantly underestimated, particularly during the NH summer (JJA) and SH winter time (JJA).
- HadGEM3-ORCA-HR simulates more storms at lower latitudes and fewer storms in higher latitudes, and the equatorward shift in simulated storm tracks is more prominent in NH winter (DJF) and SH winter (JJA).
- IFS-FESOM2 compares well with reanalyses with some underestimations in the North Atlantic and North Pacific storms tracks in summer (NH JJA), and in the storm track poleward of 60S in winter (SH JJA)
- Overall, improvements in ETC representation with increase in resolution seen in HadGEM3 and IFS.

The global distribution of wintertime storm track density in the Northern and Southern hemispheres are shown in Figures 28 and 29. The storm track in the Northern Hemisphere is separated into two main regions of high track density: the North Atlantic storm track that extends from the Rocky Mountains in North America to the north of Europe; and the North Pacific storm track that extends from East Asia into Western Northern Pacific. There is also a secondary track in the Mediterranean (Figure 28i). The higher track densities observed in the reanalysis datasets between 60°E and

120°E (Tibetan Plateau) is likely due to the use of mean sea-level pressure (MSLP) criterion for ETC detection and is not observed when estimated with relative vorticity trackers. The Tibetan Plateau is generally associated with negligible cyclone activity as the topography tends to block, diverge and suppress approaching cyclones (Ren et al. 2023, Su et al. 2024).

Overall, the atm-only models are in good agreement with reanalysis. At higher resolutions, the atm-only models tend to produce fewer storms in both the North Atlantic and North Pacific. However, in the North Pacific, the biases have a dipole structure, with positive values south of 40°N and negative biases to the north. This indicates an equatorward shift in the storm tracks with increasing resolution and has been reported in previous studies (references). The coupled HadGEM3 model has larger biases compared to its atm-only counterpart, but they are reduced at higher resolution. IFS-FESOM performs better than its atm-only counterpart (ECMWF-IFS-HR), with reduction in biases in the North Pacific and Mediterranean storm tracks. ICON is characterized by large negative biases in the North Atlantic and the Central Pacific.

Figure 28: Extratropical cyclone density from JRA3Q reanalysis during Dec-Feb in Northern Hemisphere and track density bias relative to JRA3Q in models during historical period (1983-2013). The top row shows the atm-only simulations (highresSST-present) and middle row indicates the coupled simulations. Stippling indicates regions where track density is significantly (p -value < 0.05) different from JRA3Q.

Figure 29: Same as Figure 28 but during Jun-Aug in NH.

Figure 30: Same as Figure 28 but during Dec-Feb in SH.

Figure 31: Same as Figure 28 but during Jun-Aug in SH.

4. The role of eddies in shaping the mean state

This section summarises results from atmosphere-only sensitivity experiments (*Reference* and *SmoothAnom* as described in EERIE deliverables 9.3 and 9.4), which are intended to complement the EERIE coupled simulations and are designed to isolate the response of the large-scale atmospheric circulation to the direct thermodynamic forcing attributable to extratropical SST anomalies associated with transient mesoscale features (e.g. nonlinear eddies). Simulations are conducted with two resolutions of the IFS (~28 km and ~9 km) and HadGEM3 (~60 km and ~20 km) atmosphere models with ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions specified using high-resolution satellite-based estimates of daily-mean sea SST and sea-ice concentration. Other than their treatment of ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions, the higher-resolution configurations of IFS and HadGEM3 described here are identical to the atmosphere components of the corresponding EERIE coupled simulations discussed above (IFS-NEMO/IFS-FESOM, HadGEM).

4.1 Background

Recent work has emphasised that there have been many advances in the understanding of air-sea interactions at the ocean mesoscale during the last 25 years (Seo et al., 2023). In particular, the impact of mesoscale SST anomalies on the local marine atmospheric boundary layer (MABL) is now well-established (e.g. Xie 2004; Small et al. 2008; Frenger et al. 2013; Chelton et al. 2004). There is also emerging evidence from idealised studies that mesoscale SST anomalies can modify the large-scale atmospheric circulation and associated precipitation patterns (e.g. Ma et al. 2015; Piazza et al. 2016; Ma et al. 2017; Foussard et al. 2019; Liu et al. 2021). However, the relative importance of sharp sea surface temperature (SST) gradients associated with ocean fronts and transient ocean eddies on the large-scale extratropical atmospheric circulation remains uncertain.

Several previous studies have focussed on the response of the large-scale atmospheric circulation to SST forcing associated with mesoscale ocean eddies. In particular, Ma et al. (2015, 2017) used a regional configuration of the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model to explore the response of the free troposphere and North Pacific storm track to transient mesoscale SST variability (i.e. eddies) in the Kuroshio/Oyashio Extension region. They found that the removal of mesoscale SST anomalies from model boundary conditions led to a local reduction of winter cyclogenesis intensity due to changes to moist baroclinic instability. These changes were associated with a remote response of the large-scale atmospheric circulation in the east Pacific, including a poleward shift of the storm track in the presence of ocean eddy forcing and substantial precipitation changes over the North American coast (equivalent to 20-25% of total winter rainfall in the control simulation). Importantly, these impacts were identified in higher-resolution simulations (~27 km grid spacing) but not present in lower-resolution simulations (~162 km grid spacing). This resolution sensitivity was attributed to the inability of the lower-resolution model to explicitly represent moist diabatic processes in the atmosphere (Ma et al. 2017; Willison et al. 2013).

Using a similar experimental design, Liu et al. (2021) found that mesoscale SST forcing associated with ocean eddies in the Kuroshio/Oyashio Extension region could exert a remote influence on the frequency and intensity of heavy precipitation events associated with land-falling atmospheric rivers on the west coast of North America. They highlighted the importance of the asymmetrical response of the atmosphere to warm vs cold ocean eddies, which impacted the moisture flux out of the planetary boundary layer thereby influencing the integrated vapour transports and development of extratropical cyclones.

Foussard et al (2019) also explored the impact of ocean eddies on the large-scale atmospheric circulation using a highly-idealised configuration of the WRF model. A reentrant channel configuration representative of the mid-latitude atmosphere was forced by a zonally symmetric time-independent SST front with and without mesoscale SST structures derived from a scaled snapshot of frontal turbulence in a 2D quasigeostrophic model. The authors showed that mesoscale SST structures were associated with a rectified impact on the time-mean latent heat fluxes, which moistened the boundary layer, modified the net convective heating above ocean eddies, and resulted in modest changes to zonal mean winds of $O(1)$ m/s and a poleward shift of the tropospheric jet.

From these idealised and regional modelling studies, there is emerging evidence that mid-latitude ocean eddies can have a modest but statistically significant impact on the remote atmospheric circulation. However, the evidence from state-of-the-art coupled subseasonal-to-seasonal (S2S) forecasting systems with an improved representation of mesoscale ocean eddies – either due to improved ocean initial conditions or increased ocean resolution – is more equivocal. For example, both Roberts et al. (2022) and Reynolds et al. (2025) found that an improved representation of the ocean mesoscale was associated with improved forecasts of ocean properties at S2S lead times but very limited impacts on the atmosphere.

4.2. Local atmospheric response to ocean eddies

The primary objective of this section is to evaluate the response of the large-scale atmospheric circulation to the integrated thermodynamic forcing from small-scale extratropical SST anomalies associated with transient mesoscale features (i.e., ocean eddies). A necessary foundation for this analysis is to establish that (1) our *Reference* simulations can adequately represent the local atmospheric response to extratropical ocean eddies and (2) the local imprint of ocean eddies is removed in our *SmoothAnom* simulations with idealised SST boundary conditions.

Our composite analysis of the local atmospheric response to observation-based ocean eddy locations in the Southern Ocean reveals several robust features, which are consistent with previously described mechanisms linking ocean eddy-related SST anomalies with the vertical mixing of horizontal momentum in the atmospheric boundary layer (e.g. Chelton and Xie, 2010; Frenger et al. 2013). In particular, we find that anticyclonic eddies are typically associated with positive SST anomalies, enhanced turbulent heat fluxes from the ocean to the atmosphere, increased 10 m wind speeds, and elevated precipitation (Figure 32).

Figure 32 : Composite means of sea surface temperature (SST), 10m wind speed, turbulent heat fluxes (positive out of the ocean), and total precipitation derived from daily mean $\frac{1}{4}$ degree data sampled for observed anticyclonic eddy locations from the Southern Ocean (25S-60S) calculated following Aengenheyster et al. (submitted). Before calculating composite means, each daily mean snapshot is rotated such that the large-scale winds are from left to right and resampled according to the identified eddy radius. Observational composite means are derived using ESA CCI SSTs (Embury et al., 2024), 10 m wind speed from merged scatterometer/ERA5 data (Copernicus Marine Service 2019), and precipitation from GPM-IMERG (Huffmann et al., 2019). Top four rows use the same 513397 eddy locations between 2010-2021. For high-resolution HadGEM3, 484837 eddy locations between 2000-2009 are used due to data availability.

Figure 33: As Figure 32, but for the difference between composites means of anticyclonic and cyclonic eddies. For top four rows, the same 513397 anticyclonic and 543972 cyclonic eddies are used, while for HadGEM3 484837 anticyclonic and 518408 cyclonic eddies are used.

Our estimate of the difference in precipitation between composites of anticyclonic and cyclonic eddies based on IMERG satellite data is approximately 0.2 mm day^{-1} (Figure 33). This is smaller than the estimate reported by Frenger et al. (2013) but broadly consistent with IMERG-based

estimates from Liu et al. (2018). These differences between observation-based estimates could be a consequence of differences between satellite-based precipitation products (Liu et al. 2018), sensitivity to evaluation period, or other differences in the identification, scaling, and selection of eddies used for composite calculations.

Lower- and higher-resolution *Reference* simulations from both IFS and HadGEM3 models qualitatively capture the observed composite-average precipitation and wind speed patterns associated with ocean eddies (Figure 32). These composite average patterns are qualitatively similar in lower- and higher-resolution simulations from the same model. The similarity between resolutions is stronger for IFS, while eddy-related features are generally weaker in low-resolution HadGEM3 simulations (figures 32 and 33), likely because the 60 km resolution is similar to the mean eddy radius in the Southern Ocean. However, there are some notable inter-model differences when comparing the atmospheric response to anticyclonic versus cyclonic eddies.

All simulations tend to underestimate the imprint of eddies on 10 m wind speeds relative to observations, though this underestimate is smaller for higher-resolution simulations and smallest for the high-resolution HadGEM3 simulation. Conversely, the higher resolution HadGEM3 simulation has the strongest precipitation response relative to IMERG satellite estimates. The precipitation response is weakest (closest to observations) for the high-resolution IFS simulation. HadGEM3 also systematically displays weaker winds but stronger turbulent heat fluxes over eddies (Figure 32) which points to inherent model differences. The high-resolution HadGEM3 eddy composites were available for a different period than the remaining three models and observations (2000-2009 rather than 2010-2021). Judging from the low-resolution HadGEM3 composites being available for both periods, the eddy SST signatures and some responses appear slightly higher in the later period, suggesting that the high-resolution HadGEM3 response might be slightly underestimated in Figures 32.

The atmospheric imprint of small-scale ocean eddies is effectively suppressed in the SmoothAnom experiments. This is clearly illustrated in Figure 34, which shows that the difference between anticyclonic and cyclonic eddies is strongly reduced in the SmoothAnom experiment with IFS Tco1279, with similar results obtained for other models (not shown). While our scale-selective filtering of extratropical SST anomalies does not completely eliminate the ocean eddy signature (figure 34), the composite-average impact on surface winds, turbulent heat fluxes, and precipitation is dramatically reduced compared to the corresponding Reference simulations (figure 33). From these results, we consider these experiments to be an appropriate dataset to evaluate the

large-scale atmospheric response to small-scale thermodynamic forcing from SST anomalies associated with extratropical ocean eddies.

Figure 34: As Figure 33 but for the difference between composite means in the high-resolution IFS SmoothAnom experiment.

4.3. Impact of extratropical ocean eddies on the atmospheric mean state

4.3.1. Assessment of basic impact

To assess the climatological influence of ocean eddies, we focus on seasonal mean diagnostics from the 10-member ensemble of IFS Tco399 simulations (figure 35). The ensemble averaging reduces sampling uncertainty associated with year-to-year atmospheric variability, thereby isolating the response to mesoscale ocean forcing. Statistical robustness is assessed using a paired-sample t-test ($p < 0.05$) applied to ensemble mean differences between Reference and SmoothAnom experiments. Bootstrap-based significance testing gives almost identical results (not shown). In figure 35, hatching denotes regions where differences are statistically robust in the IFS Tco399 ensemble, while stippling indicates locations where the sign of the response is consistent across all four model/resolution combinations.

IFS Tco399: Reference minus SmoothAnom (1985-2014)

Figure 35: Global maps for Reference minus SmoothAnom DJF (left) and JJA (right) seasonal means for latent heat flux, daily maximum 2m temperature, total precipitation and total cloud cover in the IFS Tco399 10-member ensemble. Hatching indicates 5% significance considering the 29 seasonal ensemble means between 1985-2014 as independent samples. Stippling indicates regions where the four simulations (high- and low-resolution IFS and HadGEM3) agree on the sign of the response.

Seasonal-mean changes in surface latent fluxes reflect asymmetries in the atmospheric response to cyclonic versus anticyclonic eddies, highlighting nonlinearities in the response to positive and negative SST anomalies. Ocean eddies enhance latent heat release from the ocean to the atmosphere by approximately 5–10 $W m^{-2}$ in regions of intense eddy activity, including the Gulf Stream, Kuroshio Extension, and Agulhas Retroflexion (figure 35). These signals are statistically

robust in the IFS Tco399 10-member ensemble, and in some cases (e.g. over the Agulhas Retroflection during JJA) are consistent across the single-member results for other models. Other significant changes to latent heat fluxes in IFS Tco399 experiments are evident in lower-latitude regions (e.g. tropical Atlantic during DJF), though these are not systematically reproduced across the other models and resolution combinations.

Our experiments indicate that extratropical ocean eddies exert a limited influence on seasonal mean 2 m air temperature (T2m; not shown). However, they systematically affect the diurnal cycle such that all models show a robust increase of ~0.5 K in seasonal mean daily maximum T2m in eddy-rich regions during both DJF and JJA (figure 35). Remote signals associated with large-scale circulation changes (figure 35) are also evident in some regions. For example, IFS Tco399 shows wintertime warming over Greenland and temperature changes over Antarctica, though only the Antarctic response is consistent across models.

Figure 36: Scatter plot of globally averaged JJA total cloud cover over a southern ocean box (see text) in coupled climate models versus their atmospheric horizontal resolution (km). The black dots are models from the CMIP multimodel ensemble (CMIP5, CMIP6 and HighResMIP). The coloured symbols are IFS-FESOM (purple square), IFS-NEMO (yellow triangle pointing down), ICON (blue diamond), HadGEM (green triangle pointing left) and ERA5 (red star). To the right is a histogram of the values for the CMIP multimodel data, with the coloured lines corresponding to the EERIE models and ERA5. The value of M is the mean across the CMIP multimodel ensemble.

In eddy-active regions, IFS Tco399 indicates a mean precipitation increase of $\sim 0.1 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$ due to ocean eddies. However, the signal is noisy in single-member simulations, limiting multi-model consensus. An exception occurs in the Agulhas Retroflection during JJA, where regionally focused precipitation increases are accompanied by small but statistically robust ($\sim 1 \%$) reductions in total cloud cover across models. We speculate that the changes in cloud cover are a consequence of an eddy-induced shift between widespread stratiform clouds towards deeper more localized convection triggered by the enhanced latent heating associated with ocean eddies. However, we note that the coupled EERIE simulations show if anything an increase in cloud cover in this region relative to lower resolution CMIP models: see Figure 36. This suggests that the eddies exert a second order impact here, with the dominant role being played by the atmosphere.

4.3.3. Gulf Stream precipitation

For a detailed investigation over a specific region, we focus on mean and extreme precipitation over the Gulf Stream region, where a consistent precipitation response was identified (Figure 35), and where the coupled EERIE simulations also show an increase in these quantities relative to lower resolution models (Figure 17).

Figure 37 shows the precipitation impact over the extended winter season NDJFM for the four experiments, highlighting the Pacific and Atlantic regions. Figure 38 shows precipitation statistics for the Gulf Stream region (35-45N, 70-50W). The AMIP simulations have mean Gulf Stream precipitation generally larger than observations, with higher values for high-resolution runs, and HadGEM higher than IFS. IFS Tco399 tends to underestimate the magnitude of Gulf Stream precipitation extremes compared to observations and the other models. Mesoscale eddies have a consistent enhancing impact on both mean and extreme precipitation in the Gulf Stream region, as demonstrated by Reference simulations showing larger magnitudes than SmoothAnom. The exception is HadGEM3 for DJF means, and high-resolution HadGEM3 for DJF extremes. In JJA, the impact is stronger, and all simulations agree on the sign of the response. The precipitation response is largely due to convective precipitation (not shown) likely caused by convection induced by mesoscale SST anomalies.

NDJFM precipitation difference between SmoothAnom minus reference: 1985-2022

IFS-AMIP, tco1279. Reference - SmoothAnom

IFS-AMIP: tco399. Reference - SmoothAnom. 10 members

HadGEM3: N640. Reference - SmoothAnom (1985-2012)

HadGEM3: N216. Reference - SmoothAnom

Figure 37: Reference minus SmoothAnom NDJFM precipitation over the Pacific and Atlantic from the four atmosphere-only simulations (10 member ensemble for IFS-AMIP tco399). A box highlights the Western US region from Figure 1 of Ma et al., 2015.

Note that the difference in precipitation extremes between the Reference and SmoothAnom simulations is, for the high resolution configurations, around 1 mm/day. Examination of the linear relationship between resolution and extremes in Figure 17b suggests this is about equivalent to the increase expected when moving from a 25km atmosphere and ¼ degree ocean to a 10km atmosphere and 1/12th degree ocean. Thus it is likely that the presence of ocean eddies is contributing to the increased precipitation extremes in the EERIE coupled simulations. However, the intermodel spread in the average magnitude of the extremes is larger than this (cf. the coloured symbols in figure 17b), suggesting that the atmospheric model (resolution and choice of convection parameterisations) plays a larger role in setting this value.

Figure 38: Precipitation statistics over the Gulf Stream (35-45N, 70-50W) from atmosphere-only simulations. (a-b) Seasonal mean, (c-d) 99th percentile of daily precipitation over DJF (left) and JJA (right) are computed point-wise based on data regridded bilinearly to a 1 degree regular grid. Each panel shows Reference simulations and GPM-IMERG on the left and SmoothAnom simulations on the right. Methodology and time period (2000-2015) is chosen to align with Figure 17.

4.3.3. Remote changes and dynamical response to eddies

We also find some evidence that ocean eddies can modulate remote precipitation. In particular, all models show a ~10 % reduction in DJF precipitation over the northeastern Pacific and the adjacent North American coast (figure 36 and 37). This signal aligns with previous regional modeling studies, which attributed similar wintertime anomalies to changes in moist baroclinic instability and a northward shift of the North Pacific storm track induced by Kuroshio eddies (Ma et al., 2015, 2017; Liu et al., 2021). There is also evidence for changes in tropical precipitation, which may reflect large-scale adjustments in the atmospheric overturning circulation and associated shifts in the intertropical convergence zone in response to changes in extratropical latent heating. However, these signals are not generally consistent across models indicating that the tropical response to extratropical ocean eddy forcing remains uncertain.

Figure 39: As figure 35, but for 500 hPa geopotential height and 300 hPa zonal and meridional wind. Hatching indicates 5% significance considering the 29 seasonal ensemble means between 1985-2014 as independent samples. Stippling indicates regions where the four simulations (high- and low-resolution IFS and HadGEM3) agree on the sign of the response.

The most compelling evidence for a large-scale dynamical response to ocean eddies emerges in the Northern Hemisphere winter (DJF; figures 36 and 37). In IFS Tco399, the North Pacific jet exhibits a statistically robust northward shift at its exit region, evident as $\sim 1 m s^{-1}$ changes in zonal mean zonal wind at 300 hPa. This is accompanied by an intensification of the climatological stationary waves in meridional winds and geopotential height (figure 39). The spatial pattern of these changes in the North Pacific is consistent across models and also with the previous regional modelling studies that have linked modulation of precipitation in the northeastern Pacific with eddy-forced changes in the North Pacific storm track.

In the wintertime North Atlantic (figures 39 and 37) there is some evidence that ocean mesoscale eddies can induce a tripole-like response in zonal winds at 300 hPa, which manifests as a $\sim 0.5 m s^{-1}$ weakening in the climatological jet exit region, with strengthening to the north and south.

Figure 40: Difference in JJA zonal mean wind due to including mesoscale SST variability in AMIP boundary condition. Shown are IFS at high-resolution (top left) and the low-resolution 10-member ensemble mean (top right), HadGEM at high-resolution (bottom left) and low-resolution (bottom right). Hatching implies significance at the 5% level, tested over the 29 seasonal means between 1985 and 2014, while stippling shows where all four panels agree on the sign of the response.

Although not statistically robust in IFS Tco399, the sign of this response is consistent across models.

Figure 40 reveals some consistent signals between the simulations in the response of JJA zonal mean zonal wind response to mesoscale eddies. The single-member simulations from IFS Tco1279 and HadGEM3 (N640, N216) consistently show a weak but statistically significant northward shift of the Northern Hemisphere summer jet around 50N. This behavior is consistent with idealized modeling studies and multimodel analysis studies that have linked extratropical latent heating anomalies to poleward jet displacements (e.g. Foussard et al., 2019 and Strommen et al., 2025). In particular, Strommen et al. (2025) argued that extreme Gulf Stream precipitation is linked to a robust poleward shift in the North Atlantic jet, and so the signal seen here may be consistent with the enhanced eddy-driven precipitation extremes seen in Figure 38. The exception to this picture is the IFS 28 km ensemble (top right) where the ensemble mean signal is nearly absent. Some ensemble members show a similar response compared to 9 km IFS which is just

outside the 28 km envelope. Whether this is coincidence or points towards a resolution sensitivity in the response of JJA zonal mean zonal winds is not yet clear.

Finally, Figures 41 and 42 show the response of the extratropical cyclone tracks to the presence of timevarying ocean eddies. The change in the North Atlantic is inconsistent and weak across both seasons. In the North Pacific DJF, if anything there is a slight suggestion that there is a reduction in the track density due to eddies (Figure 41g and h). This may be because the poleward shift of the jet (Figure 39) results in a weakening of the jet winds at the peak of the climatological track densities in this region, which may cause a slight reduction in tracks which is not compensated for due to the increased difficulty of supporting extratropical cyclones further north. However, the overall picture given by the track density analysis is that the magnitude of change is small, and likely noise in many regions. This is consistent with the magnitude of the impact of ocean eddies on the circulation being small, combined with the high sampling variability in extratropical cyclone track statistics. It is possible that with further ensemble members a more robust picture would emerge.

Figure 41: Extratropical cyclone track density (NH, DJF) bias relative to JRA3Q in EERIE atm-only models (reference and SmoothAnom) for both low and high-resolutions during historical period (1983-2013).

Figure 42: Extratropical cyclone track density (NH, JJA) bias relative to JRA3Q in EERIE atm-only models (reference and SmoothAnom) for both low and high-resolutions during historical period (1983-2013).

4.4. Summary

To summarise, we find a modest but statistically detectable response of the large-scale atmospheric circulation to the direct thermodynamic forcing attributable to extratropical SST anomalies associated with mesoscale ocean eddies. Locally, eddies enhance surface latent heat fluxes, intensify the diurnal cycle of near-surface temperatures, and promote convective precipitation at the expense of large-scale cloud cover in some regions. We also identify some remote responses, including precipitation and circulation changes in the eastern North Pacific during the winter season. These changes are consistent with previous idealized regional studies (e.g. Ma et al. 2015, 2017), which have attributed reduced precipitation along the North American coast and shifts of the North Pacific storm track to forcing from ocean eddies in the Kuroshio Extension. Other signals, such as Antarctic surface warming, North Atlantic jet adjustments, and tropical precipitation changes, are suggestive but less robust across models. Impacts on the extratropical storm tracks are generally noisy and hard to detect.

Placed in the context of previous studies (e.g. Ma et al. 2015; 2017, Foussard et al. 2019; Liu et al. 2021), our findings suggest that the direct thermodynamic forcing from ocean eddies exerts a measurable and dynamically coherent influence on some regional climate features. However, the net effect on the seasonal mean climate is rather modest compared to the magnitude of year-to-year variability. From the perspective of coupled Earth system modelling, this implies that the dominant impact of ocean eddies on the atmosphere likely arises indirectly, via their impact on ocean heat and salinity transports and associated large-scale SST biases, rather than the small-scale forcing attributable to transient mesoscale SST anomalies.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

Deliverable report D6.1 conducted an in-depth analysis of the ocean mean state and dynamics in the eddy-rich EERIE control simulations, and concluded that while significant improvements were seen in the dynamics and variability of the ocean, changes in key large-scale biases, such as SSTs and SIC, were far more ambiguous. We verified here that the SST and SIC biases are not systematically reduced in the historical simulations either, with biases on par with past CMIP6 models at lower resolution. Our assessment here of the atmospheric mean state is consistent with this picture, showing that the EERIE models exhibit large-scale biases in key variables such as T2M, precipitation and the zonally averaged circulation, which are in general comparable to typical CMIP6 biases. For example, the double-ITCZ bias is still present in the EERIE simulations with no indication that the magnitude of the bias has gone down.

Nevertheless, there are several encouraging counterpoints to this picture. The IFS-FESOM and HadGEM models perform notably well, clearly outperforming typical CMIP6 models in many aspects. While IFS-NEMO exhibits a consistent cold bias exceeding all the CMIP6 models, its biases at any given gridpoint are small and simulations with the IFS forced with prescribed SSTs and SIC performs much better than the CMIP6 models. This suggests that the bias could be removed with model tuning, and that if this were done then IFS-NEMO would plausibly also simulate an atmospheric mean state competitive with the best CMIP6 models. Furthermore, the poor performance of the ICON model is likely related to its lack of convection parameterisations, which results in biases in the tropics that overwhelm any improvement that might be arising from enhanced resolution in both the atmosphere and ocean. Thus the performance of both IFS-NEMO and ICON could likely be substantially improved with some additional model development. This

potential is corroborated by the fact that all four EERIE models perform notably well at simulating incoming and outgoing TOA radiation, continuing the clear trend of model improvements that have taken place from CMIP3 to CMIP6.

The sensitivity experiments, designed to isolate the direct effect of time-varying mesoscale eddies, suggests that the presence of eddies in the EERIE models does have a robust influence on the atmosphere. However, the effect is small in magnitude and quite localised. We identified two particularly robust impacts. Firstly, the presence of eddies results in enhanced latent heat fluxes and precipitation over eddy-rich regions such as the Gulf Stream and Kuroshio. The enhanced latent heating in these regions appears to trigger robust shifts in the North Atlantic and North Pacific jets, with the generic impact being a slight poleward shift, consistent with past literature (Foussard et al., 2019; Strommen et al., 2025). While this would be expected to have an imprint on extratropical cyclone tracks, the effect seems to be too small for any clear signature to emerge for the sample size available here. A surprising feature is that the impact in the North Atlantic appears to be greater in summer than winter, though it is possible this is because the larger internal variability in winter masks a signal of comparable magnitude to the small one found in summer. Secondly, the presence of eddies results in a year-round reduction in total cloud cover over the southern ocean, which is again likely a consequence of enhanced latent heating due to eddies resulting in changes to the southern hemisphere jet and vertical stratification. These changes are supported by eddy composite analysis, which show that eddies have a clear local impact on the atmosphere.

In all these cases we emphasise that the magnitude of the changes are modest compared to interannual variability. They are also much smaller than the spread between the coupled EERIE models, and sometimes opposite to the direction of change between the coupled 10km EERIE models and CMIP models at lower atmospheric resolution. For example, the eddy-rich EERIE models have greater southern ocean cloud cover than lower resolution models, contradicting the robust reduction diagnosed with the sensitivity experiments. We also emphasise that there are many regions and variables for which no robust impact of the eddies are found. These results are consistent with past forecast studies showing little impact on atmospheric skill from resolving mesoscale eddies (Roberts et al. 2022; Reynolds et al. 2025).

To summarise, we draw the following key conclusions from this report. Firstly, it is likely that the dominant impact of ocean eddies on the atmosphere arises indirectly, via the way they change the large-scale SST biases in models by modulating ocean heat and salinity transports, as opposed to via the direct forcing attributable to transient mesoscale eddies. Secondly, these indirect effects are

themselves intimately coupled with atmospheric, non-eddy-related biases, and these latter dominate the overall atmospheric mean state of the models. As a result, improvements due to resolving eddies are not always clear in the EERIE coupled models, with their mean state biases on a whole being comparable to past CMIP6 models. This reinforces past experience that model tuning and calibration is an essential exercise in order to realise the full potential of enhanced resolution (Moreno-Chamarro et al. 2021) and that much could be gained by developing faster methods for tuning high-resolution models. Finally, given that clear improvements in the ocean variability are seen in the eddy-rich EERIE models (see report D61) it is possible that a more unequivocal improvement will be detectable in atmospheric variability, something which will be examined in the upcoming Deliverable D7.2. The present report is an essential first step in this direction and will inform future work in the EERIE project.

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Supplementary Material

Model name	Ensemble members	Nominal resolution (km)
ACCESS-CM2	r1i1p1f1	140
AWI-ESM-1-1-LR	r1i1p1f1	250
BCC-CSM2	r1i1p1f1	100
CanESM5	r1i1p1f1	250
CESM2-FV2	r1i1p1f1	250
CESM2	r1i1p1f1	100
CESM2-WACCM-FV2	r1i1p1f1	250
CESM2-WACCM	r1i1p1f1	100
CNRM-CM6-1	r1i1p1f2	140
CNRM-CM6-1-HR	r1i1p1f2	50
CNRM-ESM2	r1i1p1f2	140
EC-Earth3	r1i1p1f1	80
FGOALS-g3	r1i1p1f1	190
FGOALS-f3-K	r1i1p1f1	100
GFDL-CM4	r1i1p1f1	100
GISS-E2-1-G	r1i1p1f1	250
HadGEM3-GC31-L	r1i1p1f3	140
HadGEM3-GC31-MM	r1i1p1f3	100
INM-CM4-8	r1i1p1f1	150
INM-CM5-0	r1i1p1f1	150
IPSL-CM6A-LR	r1i1p1f1	160
MIROC6	r1i1p1f1	120
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	r1i1p1f1	80
MPI-ESM1-2-LR	r1i1p1f1	170
MRI-ESM2-0	r1i1p1f1	100
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Table 1. CMIP6 models used in this paper, along with our crude estimate of the nominal atmospheric resolution (km).

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Model name	Ensemble members	Nominal resolution (km)
NorESM2-LM	r1i1p1f1	190
NorESM2-MM	r1i1p1f1	100
TaiESM1	r1i1p1f1	100
UKESM1-0-LL	r1i1p1f2	140

Model name	Ensemble members	Nominal resolution (km)
ACCESS1-0	r1i1p1	210
ACCESS1-3	r1i1p1	210
BCC-CSM1-1	r1i1p1	310
BCC-CSM1-1-m	r1i1p1	125
BNU-ESM	r1i1p1	310
CanESM2	r[1,2,3,4,5]i1p1	310
CCSM4	r6i1p1	140
CMCC-CESM	r1i1p1	410
CMCC-CM	r1i1p1	85
CMCC-CMS	r1i1p1	410
CMCC-CM5	r1i1p1	160
EC-EARTH	r[1,2,7,9,12]i1p1	125
FGOALS-g2	r[1,3]i1p1	310
GFDL-CM3	r[1,2,3]i1p1	280
HadCM3	r[1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10]i1p1	410
HadGEM2	r[1,2,3]i1p1	210
IPSL-CM5A-LR	r[1,2,3,4,5,6]i1p1	410
IPSL-CM5A-MR	r[1,2,3]i1p1	280
IPSL-CM5B-LR	r1i1p1	410
MIROC5	r[1,2,3,4,5]i1p1	160
MIROC-ESM	r[1,2,3]i1p1	310
MPI-ESM-LR	r[1,2,3]i1p1	210
MPI-ESM-MR	r[1,2,3]i1p1	210
MPI-ESM-P	r[1,2]i1p1	210
MRI-CGCM3	r1i1p1	125
MRI-ESM1	r1i1p1	125
NorESM1-M	r[1,2,3]i1p1	280

Table 2. CMIP5 models used in this paper, along with our crude estimate of the nominal atmospheric resolution (km).

Model name	Ensemble members	Nominal resolution (km)
AWI-CM-1-1-LR	r1i1p1f002	250
AWI-CM-1-1-HR	r1i1p1f002	100
CMCC-CM2-HR4	r1i1p1f1	100
CMCC-CM2-VHR4	r1i1p1f2	25
CNRM-CM6-1	r[1,2]i1p1f2	250
CNRM-CM6-1-HR	r1i1p1f1	50
EC-Earth3	r[1,2,3]i1p2f1	100
EC-Earth3-HR	r[1,2,3]i1p2f1	50
ECMWF-IFS-LR	r[1,2,3,4,5,6]i1p1f2	50
ECMWF-IFS-MR	r[1,2,3]i1p1f2	50
ECMWF-IFS-HR	r[1,2,3,4,5,6]i1p1f2	25
HadGEM-GC31-LL	r[1,2,3,4,5,6,7]i1p1f1	250
HadGEM-GC31-MM	r1i1p1f1	100
HadGEM-GC31-HM	r[1,2,3]i1p1f1	50
HadGEM-GC31-HH	r1i1p1f1	50
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	r1i1p1f1	100
MPI-ESM1-2-XR	r1i1p1f3	50

Table 3. HighResMIP models used in this paper, along with our crude estimate of the nominal atmospheric resolution (km).

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